

THE IMPORTANCE OF DIDACTIC GAMES IN TEACHING THE UZBEK LANGUAGE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11472408>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 21-may 2024 yil

Ma'qullandi: 25-may 2024 yil

Nashr qilindi: 31-may 2024 yil

KEY WORDS

didactics, education, pedagogue, information, technology, language, speech, meaning, memory, interactive, critical thinking

ABSTRACT

This article covers the importance of didactic games in teaching the Uzbek language.

Introduction:

Today, the educational process is mainly carried out in a traditional way, but the use of modern technologies in order to achieve more achievements in education makes the use of interactive methods, graphic organizers and didactic games more effective in the classroom. Organization of in-depth study of the Uzbek language at all stages of the system, as well as improvement of teachers' qualifications and provision of modern educational and methodological materials require further improvement. It is appropriate to educate the growing young generation in a spirit of deep respect and reverence for the Uzbek language and Uzbek cultural heritage by introducing advanced methods of education with modern pedagogy and information-communication.

If traditional methods are used in lessons, if they are made interesting, this not only ensures the quality of the lesson, but also prevents boredom and attracts passive students to participate in the lesson.

Educational games are of great importance in the educational process, including mother tongue education. During our research, when we used the following educational didactic games in the course of the lesson, students' learning of science was more effective than traditional lessons.

"Train" game. Each word of a sentence is written separately on separate pieces of paper in the form of train carriages and mixed up. The task of the students is to type the wagons in such a way that the result is a correct sentence. For example: our class is located on the second floor. Correct answer: Our classroom is on the second floor.

"Remember" game. A small text is read to the students through a cassette. Students write down key words and then use those words to reconstruct the listening text. The one whose text is complete and correct will receive high marks. This game helps to strengthen the memory of students.

"Vowels" game. This name can be changed based on any theme. An optional text of educational importance is shown on a large screen, and the task is to determine the number of vowels in the text as quickly and completely as possible. Because this topic is relatively simple.

"Find it yourself" game. It is said that an image from an optional fairy tale will be shown on the basis of the topics passed through the projector. Students (3 people) are invited. Pupils stand facing the image upside down. The rest of the students tell one piece of information related to the fairy tale. Students can say the name of the story before or after, depending on their level of knowledge.

"Hashar" game. A picture is hung on the board. Each group should create a text by "hashar" (that is, each group member joins his sentence) by looking at the picture. The group that wrote the text quickly and beautifully gets one point. When evaluating the performance of these tasks (game-tasks) by the groups, students' use of words, creative thinking, creative abilities, fluency of speech are taken into account, and the group with the most points at the end of the lesson is the winner. will be announced.

Therefore, it is necessary for students to think and speak independently in any situation. There are many forms of such activity. One of them is to address students with problematic questions. In this case, it is appropriate to ask the student not questions based on ready-made information, but questions that encourage thinking, deep reflection, and independently answer the result of the reflection.

For example, it is possible to create such a problematic situation in the lessons of the Phonetics department:

1 - assignment. Each of you try to make speech sounds. Which speech organs are involved in their formation? It can be seen that not all students can pronounce speech sounds in the same way. Each of them will answer in his own way. Speech organs involved in the formation of speech sounds: "F" - when pronouncing the consonant, the lower lip approaches the upper teeth, but does not close. But the consonant "F" in words like "he puffed" is formed as a result of two lips coming together and air passing through the gap. Such situations should be fulfilled by the students themselves.

2 - assignment. Which of your speech organs are actively involved in the pronunciation of speech sounds? Here, the question is not about a specific phoneme (sound), but about sounds in general. It forces the student to think and choose his own characteristics.

Above, we gave examples of tasks, games, grammar games, riddles intended for repetition and re-memorization. These, we think, will serve as a guide for teachers. Based on such principles, they can create as many games and tasks as they want and use them during the lesson.

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